

ALLELOPATHY AND SOLARIZATION IN ORGANIC WEED CONTROL

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ABSTRACT

Organic weed management is a system that incorporates the use of diverse biological organisms and biologically-based approaches including solarization, allelopathy, crop competition, and other cultural practices to significantly reduce weed densities in a manner that is similar to use of chemical herbicides alone. Interest in developing effective biological weed management systems continues to increase because of a growing awareness of problems associated with the constant and intensive use of chemical herbicides, which include surface- and groundwater contamination, detrimental impacts on nontarget organisms, development of weeds resistant to herbicides, and consumer concerns for residues on food. Among different biological methods of weed control, allelopathy and soil solarization could lead to reduced labour costs and increased efficiency, without any adverse effects on the environment.

The paper highlights the different concepts of using allelopathy and soil solarization for eco-friendly control of weeds.

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

Weeds are wild plants that grow at unwanted places such as fields and interfere with the growth of cultivated plants. Approximately 30,000 plant species are identified as weeds. Among them, 250 are really important and about 80 are known to reduce crop yield.

Weeds have substantially adapted characteristics (e.g. produce an abundance of seed, rapid seedling growth, quick maturation, dual modes of reproduction, environmental plasticity) that enable them to grow, flourish, invade and dominate an important part of natural and agricultural ecosystems. In agro-ecosystems, weeds compete with crop plants for resources, interfere in crop handling, reduce crop yield and deteriorate their quality, and thus result in huge financial losses. Degree of loss depends on crop species present, timing and duration of competitive interactions, and resource availability. Weeds, pathogens and animal pests cause a loss of around 13.2, 13.3 and 15.6% (totally 42.1%), respectively, in the eight most important food and cash crops, even when they are intensively controlled. However, if no physical, biological or chemical measures were used to protect crops, yield losses would be around 69.8%. So, losses prevented by crop protection measures are about 27.6% of attainable production. In light of these characteristics of weeds and their hazards, it becomes imperative to control them.

Several techniques (e.g. mechanical and chemicals) are used for weed control. These techniques attempt to achieve a balance between cost of control and crop yield loss. Mechanical methods, such as hand weeding require enormous labour and time input. Nowadays, chemical method provides an effective strategy for weed control. Since their discovery in the 1950s, synthetic herbicides have developed as a major tool for weed management. Herbicides have helped farmers to increase yields while reducing labour. Indeed, without herbicides, labour would be a major cost of crop production in developed countries. Nevertheless, the indiscriminate use of herbicides has provoked an increasing incidence of resistance in weeds to some herbicides, changes in weed population to species more related to the crop, environmental pollution, and potential health hazards. Overuse of synthetic chemicals for weed control worsens the quality of soil, water, other life support systems, human health and food. Fast-developing herbicide-

resistant ecotypes of weeds are also posing serious threats to agricultural production. Because of all these problems, efforts are being made to find out alternative low-input strategies for weed management.

It is imperative to concentrate on research to find out some natural, alternative low-input strategies for weed management, thereby minimizing or avoiding the frequent use of herbicides in future. In this regard allelopathic effect of different plants is drawing attention of many researchers in the recent past. Soil solarization as well is beginning to draw attention worldwide.

CHAPTER TWO

SOIL SOLARIZATION AS ORGANIC WEED CONTROL

2.1 SOIL SOLARIZATION.

Soil borne pests can be controlled in vegetable and fruit crops by pre-plant application of pesticides, including the fumigants methyl bromide, chloropicrin, and metam sodium. The use of these materials, however, is often undesirable due to their toxicity to animals and people, their residual toxicity in plants and soils, the complexity of soil treatment, and their high cost.

Furthermore, restrictions on the use of soil-applied pesticides seem imminent as existing environmental legislation is implemented. As a result, there has been an increased emphasis on reduced-pesticide or non pesticidal control methods.

Soil solarization is non-chemical and environmentally friendly method of using solar power for controlling pests such as soilborne plant pathogens including fungi, bacteria, nematodes, and insect and mite pests along with weed seed and seedlings in the soil by mulching the soil and covering it with tarp, usually with a transparent polyethylene cover, to trap solar energy. It may also describe methods of decontaminating soil using using high temperatures produced by capturing radiant energy from the sunlight or solar power. This energy causes physical, chemical, and biological changes in the soil.

Solarization during the hot summer months can increase soil temperature to levels that kill many disease-causing organisms (pathogens), nematodes, and weed seed and seedlings. It leaves no toxic residues and can be easily used on a small or large scale. Soil solarization also improves soil structure and increases the availability of nitrogen (N) and other essential plant nutrients.

Soil solarization can be combined with organic soil amendments or reduced rates of pesticide application for greater effectiveness. Large increases in plant growth, harvestable yield, and crop quality often occur in solarized soil and may continue for more than one growing season. The potential for using soil solarization to control diseases and pests in the warmer areas have been found to be excellent.

2.2 BRIEF HISTORY OF SOLARIZATION

Attempts were made to use solar energy for controlling disease agents in soil and in plant material already in the ancient civilization of India. In 1939, Groashevoy, who used the term "solar energy for sand disinfection," controlled *Thielaviopsis basicola* upon heating the sand by exposure to direct sunlight.

Soil solarization is the third approach for soil disinfestation; the two other main approaches, soil steaming and fumigation; were developed at the end of the 19th century. The idea of solarization was based on observations by extension workers and farmers in the hot Jordan Valley, who noticed the intensive heating of the polyethylene-mulched soil. In 1977, American scientists from the University of California at Davis reported the control of *Verticillium* in a cotton field, based on studies started in 1976, thus denoting, for the first time, the possible wide applicability of this method.

The use of polyethylene for soil solarization differs in principle from its traditional agricultural use. With solarization, soil is mulched during the hottest months (rather than the coldest, as in conventional plasticulture which is aimed at protecting the crop) in order to increase the maximal temperatures in an attempt to achieve lethal heat levels.

In the first 10 years following the influential 1976 publication, soil solarization was investigated in at least 24 countries and has been now been applied in more than 50, mostly in the hot regions, although there were some important exceptions. Studies have demonstrated effectiveness of solarization with various crops, including vegetables, field crops, ornamentals and fruit trees, against many pathogens, weeds and a soil arthropod. Those pathogens and weeds which are not controlled by solarization were also detected.

The biological, chemical and physical changes that take place in solarized soil during and after the solarization have been investigated, as well as the interaction of solarization with other methods of control. Long-term effects including biological control and increased growth response were verified in various climatic regions and soils, demonstrating the general applicability of solarization. Computerized simulation models have been developed to guide researchers and growers whether the ambient conditions of their locality are suitable for solarization. Studies of the improvement of solarization by integrating it with other methods or

by solarizing in closed glasshouses, or studies concerning commercial application by developing mulching machines were also carried out.

The use of solarization in existing orchards (e.g. controlling *Verticillium* in pistachio plantations) is an important deviation from the standard pre-planting method and was reported as early as 1979.

2.3 HOW TO SOLARIZE SOIL

2.3.1 Soil Preparation

Solarization is most effective when the plastic sheeting (tarp) is laid as close as possible to a smooth soil surface. Preparation of the soil begins by disking, tilling, or turning the soil by hand to break up clods and then smoothing the soil surface. Remove any large rocks, weeds, or any other objects or debris that will raise or puncture the plastic.

2.3.2 Laying the Plastic

Plastic sheets may be laid by hand or machine. The open edges of the plastic sheeting should be anchored to the soil by burying the edges in a shallow trench around the treated area. Plastic is laid either in complete coverage, where the entire field or area to be planted is treated, or strip coverage, where only beds or selected portions of the field are treated.

2.3.3 Complete coverage

In complete coverage, plastic sheeting is laid down to form a continuous surface over the entire field or area to be planted. The edges of the sheets may be joined with an ultraviolet (UV)-resistant glue or anchored by laying adjacent strips of plastic and burying both edges in soil. Anchoring the edges in the soil may be more cost effective initially than gluing the edges together but may also result in untreated soil being close to subsequently planted crops. The ends of the sheets should be held in place by burying them in the soil. If beds are formed after complete coverage, care must be taken to avoid deep tillage that could bring untreated soil to the surface. Complete coverage is recommended if the soil is heavily infested with pathogens,

nematodes, or perennial weeds, since there is less chance of re-infestation by soil being moved to the plants through cultivation or furrow-applied irrigation water.

2.3.4 Strip coverage.

In strip coverage, plastic is applied in strips over preformed beds. Strips should be a minimum of 30 inches (75 cm) wide; beds up to 5 feet (1.5 m) wide are preferred because several crop rows can be planted per bed. In some cases, strip coverage may be more practical and economical than complete coverage because less plastic is needed and it is not necessary to join the edges of the plastic sheets together. Strip coverage effectively kills most pests and eliminates the need for deep cultivation after solarization. It is especially effective against weeds, since the furrows are cultivated. With strip coverage, however, longterm control of soil pathogens and nematodes may be lost because pests in the untreated soil in the rows between the strips can contaminate and reinfested areas.

2.3.5 Irrigation

Wet soil conducts heat better than dry soil and makes soil organisms more vulnerable to heat. The soil under the plastic sheets must be saturated to at least 70 percent of field capacity in the upper layers and moist to depths of 24 inches (60 cm) for soil solarization to be effective.

Soil may be irrigated either before or after the plastic sheets are laid. If the soil is irrigated beforehand, the plastic must be applied as soon as possible to avoid water loss; if heavy machinery is used to lay the plastic, however, the soil must be dry enough to avoid compaction. If the soil is to be irrigated after the plastic is laid, one or more hose or pipe outlets may be installed under one end of the plastic; drip lines may be installed before the plastic is laid; or irrigation water may be run underneath the plastic in furrows or in the tracks made by tractor wheels if the plastic sheets were applied by machine. Fields treated by strip coverage can be irrigated by drip lines on or in the bed.

The soil does not usually need to be irrigated again during solarization, although if the soil is very light and sandy, or if the soil moisture is less than 50 percent of field capacity, it may be necessary to irrigate a second time. This will cool the soil, but because of the increased moisture the final temperatures will be greater.

2.3.6 Duration of Treatment

The plastic sheets should be left in place for 4 to 6 weeks to allow the soil to heat to the greatest depth possible. To control the most resistant species, leave the plastic in place for 6 weeks. Experience has shown that there is little or no need to take the temperature of the soil. The greatest concern is to solarize the soil during a period of high solar radiation with little wind or cloud cover. Soil in the Central Valley can be solarized for 4 weeks any time from late May to September. In coastal areas the best time may be August to September or May to June, transitional periods when fog or wind may be at a minimum.

2.3.7 Removal of the Plastic and Planting

After solarization is complete, the plastic may be removed before planting. Or, the plastic may be left on the soil as a mulch for the following crop by transplanting plants through the plastic. Clear plastic may be painted white or silver to cool the soil and repel flying insect pests in the following crop. A disadvantage of leaving the plastic on the soil is that it may degrade and be difficult to clean up in the spring. Treated soil can be planted immediately to a fall or winter crop or left fallow without the plastic until the next growing season. If the soil must be cultivated for planting, the cultivation must be shallow-less than 2 inches (5 cm)-to avoid moving viable weed seed to the surface.

2.3.8 Orchards and Vineyards

Soil solarization is most effective before or during establishment of new orchards or vineyards. It has been successfully used on a large scale to reduce *Verticillium* wilt symptoms in young pistachio orchards in California and has also been successfully used in vineyards and in avocado, stone fruit, citrus, and olive orchards in the state.

In the orchard or vineyard, clear plastic is either laid by hand around the bases of individual trees or vines and connected to strips laid between the rows or laid in anchored strips and glued along the tree rows. For best results, begin solarization as soon as trees are planted. Partial shading by young trees does not prevent soil heating, nor does soil solarization appear to bother most young trees during treatment.

However, solarizing certain species of trees, such as herbaceous perennials, avocado, and young *Prunus* trees, with clear plastic may result in plant damage, especially when trees are young. (The *Prunus* trees were killed by clear plastic but not by black film.)

In addition to killing soilborne pests, solarization of orchards and vineyards can greatly reduce the amount of water needed for irrigation and increase the growth, large commercial orchards, the cost of postplant solarization should be compared to the benefits before making a treatment decision. Experience has shown that pests that are not eradicated by solarization may recolonize roots and soil, and pathogens and nematodes may survive in roots remaining in the soil. Periodic retreatment may be necessary.

2.4 RESULTS OF SOLARIZATION

2.4.1 Increased Soil Temperature

The heating effect of soil solarization is greatest at the surface of the soil and decreases with depth. The maximum temperature of soil solarized in the field is usually from 108° to 131°F (42° to 55°C) at a depth of 2 inches (5 cm) and from 90° to 99°F (32° to 37°C) at 18 inches (45 cm).

Control of soil pests is usually best in the upper 4 to 12 inches (10-30 cm). Higher soil temperatures and deeper soil heating may be achieved inside greenhouses or by using a double layer of plastic sheeting. Soil solarized in greenhouses may reach 140°F (60°C) at a depth of 4 inches (10 cm) and 127°F (53°C) at 8 inches (20 cm). Soil solarized in black plastic nursery sleeves under a single or double layer of clear plastic can exceed 158°F (70°C).

2.4.2 Improved Soil Physical and Chemical

Solarization initiates changes in the physical and chemical features of soil that improve the growth and development of plants. It speeds up the breakdown of organic material in the soil, resulting in the release of soluble nutrients such as nitrogen (NO₃, NH₄⁺), calcium (Ca⁺⁺), magnesium (Mg⁺⁺), potassium (K⁺), and fulvic acid, making them more available to plants. Improvements in soil tilth through soil aggregation are also observed.

2.4.3 Control of Pests

Repeated daily heating during solarization kills many plant pathogens, nematodes, and weed seed and seedlings. The heat also weakens many organisms that can withstand solarization, making them more vulnerable to heat-resistant fungi and bacteria that act as natural enemies. Changes in the soil chemistry during solarization may also kill or weaken some soil organisms.

2.4.4 Sensitivity to Solarization

Although many soil pests are killed at temperatures above 86° to 91°F (30° to 33°C), plant pathogens, weeds, and other soil borne organisms differ in their sensitivity to soil heating. Some pests that are difficult to control with soil fumigants are easily controlled by soil solarization. Other pests are also affected but cannot be consistently controlled by solarization. These may require additional control measures.

2.4.5 Weeds.

Soil solarization controls many annual and perennial weeds. While some weed species are very sensitive to soil solarization, others are moderately resistant and require optimum conditions (good soil moisture, tight-fitting plastic, and high radiation) for control.

Winter annual weeds seem to be especially sensitive to solarization, and control of winter annuals is often evident for more than one year following treatment. Soil solarization is especially effective in controlling weeds in fall-seeded crops such as onions, garlic, carrots, broccoli and other brassica crops, and lettuce. White sweetclover (*Melilotus alba*) is one of the few winter annuals that is poorly controlled.

Although summer annual weeds are less temperature-sensitive than winter annuals, most summer annuals are relatively easily controlled by soil solarization. Control of purslane (*Portulaca oleracea*) and crabgrass (*Digitaria sanguinalis*) may be more difficult to achieve. If purslane is controlled, it is a good indicator that the soil has been adequately heated.

Solarization generally does not control perennial weeds as well as it controls annual weeds because perennials often have deeply buried underground vegetative structures such as roots and rhizomes that may resprout. Seed of bermudagrass (*Cynodon dactylon*), johnsongrass (*Sorghum*

halepense), and field bindweed (*Convolvulus arvensis*) are controlled by solarization. Rhizomes of bermudagrass and johnsongrass may be controlled by solarization if they are not deeply buried.

Solarization alone is not effective for the control of the rhizomes of field bindweed. Yellow nutsedge (*Cyperus esculentus*) is only partially controlled by soil solarization. Purple nutsedge (*Cyperus rotundus*) is not significantly affected; marginal solarization has actually induced purple nutsedge to grow.

2.4.6 Increased Plant Growth

Plants often grow faster and produce both higher and better-quality yields when grown in solarized soil (see color plate 4 and figure 10). This can be attributed, in part, to improved disease and weed control; but increases in plant growth are still seen when soil apparently free of pests is solarized. A number of factors may be involved. First, minor or unknown pests may also be controlled. Second, the increase in soluble nutrients improves plant growth. Third, relatively greater populations of helpful soil microorganisms have been documented following solarization, and some of these, such as certain fluorescent pseudomonad and *Bacillus* bacteria, are known to be biological control agents.

2.5 FACTORS THAT LIMIT EFFECTIVENESS OF SOLARIZATION

2.5.1 Location

Soil solarization is most effective in warm, sunny locations. It also has however been used successfully, but less predictably, in the cooler coastal areas of California and in many cooler parts of North America during periods of highest air temperatures and clear skies. Greenhouse, nursery, and seedbed (containerized) media solarization are more effective in cooler climates than field solarization.

2.5.2 Weather

Highest soil temperatures occur when days are long, air temperatures are high, skies are clear, and there is no wind. The soil heating effect may be limited on cloudy days. Wind or air movement across the plastic will rapidly dissipate the trapped heat. Also, strong winds may lift or tear sheets.

2.5.3 Timing

The best time for solarization of soil in California is from June to August, although good results may be obtained in May and September, depending on weather and location. The heat peak in many areas in temperate regions is around July 15. To maximize production, soil solarization should be done during a period in crop rotations when fields are idle.

2.5.4 Duration of Treatment

The longer the soil is heated, the better the control of pests will be. However, heating the soil longer than required for effective control (6 to 8 weeks) may be deleterious to the soil. Although some pest organisms are killed within 14 days, 4 to 6 weeks of treatment in full sun during the summer is recommended for field application.

Solarization of containerized growth media and greenhouses may be done in a few days during the heat of summer. Some relatively heat-resistant organisms may require longer (up to 8 weeks) solarization for control. The combination of pesticides, fertilizers, and certain organic amendments with solarization may reduce the needed treatment time.

2.5.5 Soil Preparation

A smooth seedbed is ideal for solarization. Air pockets between the plastic and the soil greatly reduce soil heating. Solarization will be ineffective if the seedbed is not smooth and the plastic does not rest directly on the soil.

2.5.6 Soil Moisture Content

If the soil is too dry (less than 70 percent of field capacity), weed seed and pathogens may not imbibe enough water to make them vulnerable to the increased heat.

2.5.7 Soil Color

Dark soils absorb more solar radiation than lighter colored soils and reach higher temperatures during solarization. However, adding dark material, such as charcoal, to a light loam soil has only raised maximum temperatures 1° to 2°F. Organic material such as manure may give the same limited effect.

2.5.8 Orientation of Beds

The heating of soil in raised beds will be most uniform if the beds are oriented north to south rather than from east to west. More uniform heating gives better control of pests. Solarization is most effective when there is no slope or when the slope has a south or southwest exposure. Lower temperatures and poor control of pests will occur on north-facing slopes.

Cultivation deeper than 3 inches (7.5 cm) after soil solarization should be avoided because it may bring weed seed and pathogens to the upper soil layer, causing severe weed and disease problems.

2.5.9 Integrity of Plastic Sheeting

Holes or tears in the plastic will adversely affect solarization. Animals and people should be prevented or discouraged from walking on or otherwise disturbing the plastic.

2.6 ECONOMICS OF SOLARIZATION

The cost of soil solarization depends on the thickness of the plastic used, the area of soil covered, the method of irrigation, and the method of plastic application, connection, and removal. These costs should be balanced against alternative methods of pest control, and in some cases should be viewed over a period of more than one year or growing season. In general, the greatest economic return from soil solarization will be obtained from high-value crops grown in soils infested with pathogens, nematodes, or weeds.

2.7 ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF SOLARIZATION.

2.7.1 Advantages

- Non pesticidal and simple
- No health or safety problems associated with use
- No registration is required
- Crops produced are pesticide-free and may command a higher market price
- Controls multiple soil borne diseases and pests
- Selects for beneficial microorganisms
- Tends to increase soil fertility
- Increases soluble NO₃, NH, Ca, Mg, K and soluble organic matter
- May improve soil filth
- Can speed up in-field composting of green manure

2.7.2 Disadvantages.

- May be less effective in cooler coastal areas
- Land must be taken out of production for 4 to 6 weeks during the summer
- May not fit in with some cropping cycles
- May be difficult for those using a small amount of land intensively
- Limited number of retail outlets for UV-inhibiting plastics
- Disposal may be a problem
- Large amounts of plastic cannot currently be recycled in California
- Some pests are not controlled or are difficult to control
- No pest control in the furrows between strips (if applied in strip coverage)
- High winds and animals may tear the plastic.

CHAPTER THREE

ALLELOPATHY IN ORGANIC WEED CONTROL

3.1 BACKGROUND

The phenomenon of allelopathy, whereby a plant species chemically interferes with the germination, growth or development of other plant species has been known and documented for over 2000 years.

The term allelopathy, however, was first coined in 1937 by the Austrian Professor Hans Molisch from two Greek words: allelon 'of each other' and pathos 'to suffer' and means the "injurious effect of one organism upon the other". Today, the term is generally accepted to cover both inhibitory and stimulatory effects of one plant on another plant. In 1996, the International Allelopathy Society defined allelopathy as follows: "The science that studies any process involving secondary metabolites produced by plants, micro-organisms, viruses, and fungi that influence growth and development of agricultural and biological systems (excluding animals)". Nowadays, allelopathy has a significant role in research involving sustainable agriculture, like biological weed and pest control. The current trend is to find a biological solution to minimize the perceived hazardous impacts from herbicides and insecticides in agriculture production. In this regards, the harmful impact of allelopathy can be exploited for pest and weed control.

The chemicals responsible for the phenomenon of allelopathy are generally referred to as allelochemicals or phytotoxins. Allelochemicals are usually classified as secondary metabolites and are produced as offshoots in the primary metabolic pathways of plants. Many such natural compounds have the potential to induce a wide array of biological effects and can provide great benefits to agriculture and weed management.

3.2 ALLELOCHEMICALS

Chemicals that impose allelopathic influences are called allelochemicals or allelochemicals. In a review of the potential use of allelochemicals as herbicides, Putnam (1988) listed 6 classes of allelochemicals namely alkaloids, benzoxazinones, cinnamic acid derivatives, cyanogenic compounds, ethylene and other seed germination stimulants, and flavonoids which had been

isolated from over 30 families of terrestrial and aquatic plants. All these chemicals possess actual or potential phytotoxicity. According to Rice (1984) tens of thousands of secondary substances out of several hundreds of low molecular weight compounds of primary metabolism are known today, but only a limited number has been recognized as allelochemicals. Rainfall causes the leaching of allelopathic substances from leaves which fall to the ground during period of stress; leading to inhibition of growth and germination of crop plant.

Biodegradable natural plant products rarely contain halogenated atoms and possess structural diversity and complexity, constituting one such class of chemicals and these can act directly as herbicides or may provide lead structures for herbicidal discovery. Selection of allelopathic plants is a good and commonly used approach for identification of plants with biologically active natural products.

The readily visible effects of allelochemicals on the growth and development of plants include inhibited or retarded germination rate; seeds darkened and swollen; reduced root or radicle and shoot or coleoptiles extension; swelling or necrosis of root tips; curling of the root axis; discoloration, lack of root hairs; increased number of seminal roots; reduced dry weight accumulation; and lowered reproductive capacity.

These gross morphological effects may be secondary manifestations of primary events, caused by a variety of more specific effects acting at the cellular or molecular level in the receiver plant.

In order to have any effect on the target plant the allelochemicals have to be released from the donor plant. This can happen in different ways:

1. Runoff and leachate from leaves and stem of plants. As for example, the allelochemicals in the leaves of black walnut, *Juglans nigra*, which are washed off with rain can inhibit the growth of the vegetation under the walnut tree.

2. Volatile phytotoxic compounds from the green parts of a plant, e.g. *Salvia leucophylla* and *Artemisia californica*.

3. Phytotoxic compounds from decomposing plant material, such as rye (*Secale cereale*) when used as a mulching material. Apart from shading and keeping the soil moist, rye mulch also inhibits both germination and growth of weeds through release of phytotoxins.

4. Phytotoxic compounds released from the plant roots. Rice is an example, where living rice plants are able to suppress weed growth selectively.

3.2.1 Allelochemicals and natural herbicides

There is increasing evidence that allelochemicals or natural plant products derived from higher plants/microbes can be ideal agrochemicals. Initially, the reason why plants devote resources to the production of these compounds was not understood as they were regarded as functionless waste products. It is now increasingly accepted, however, that these compounds function as defensive agents against pathogens, insects and neighbouring plants. Many such natural compounds have the potential to induce a wide array of biological effects and can provide great benefits to agriculture and weed management. Evidence showed that higher plants release a diversity of allelochemicals into the environment. Despite so much chemical diversity, allelochemicals can be broadly characterized into phenolics and terpenoids. They are released by volatilization, root exudation, death and decay of plants, and leachate from living or decaying residues. After release, allelochemicals are involved in a variety of metabolic processes. Several factors determine their toxicity such as concentration, flux rate, age and metabolic state of plant, and prevailing climatic and environmental conditions. Their amount and production varies in quality and quantity with age, cultivar, plant organ, and time of the year. Einhellig mentioned that both abiotic (temperature, nutrient amount, and moisture deficit) and biotic (disease and insect damage and interaction of plants with herbivory) factors enhance the amount and biosynthesis of allelochemicals in plants.

These allelopathic chemicals are produced by a 'donor' and transmitted to a 'receiver' that can either be 'injured' or 'stimulated'. Allelochemicals act through direct interference with physiological functions of 'receiver' such as seed germination, root growth, shoot growth, stem growth, symbiotic effectiveness or act indirectly through additive or synergistic impact along with pathological infections, insect injury and/or environmental stress. Though many of these allelochemicals exhibit inhibitory response on various morpho-physiological functions of receiver plants and such responses being observed to be dose dependant in a linear fashion, their concentrations required for control of weeds on a field scale are impracticably higher.

3.3 ALLELOPATHIC PLANTS

Rye is the most important crop plants that can effectively suppress weed growth. In one study it was found that the residue of plant shoots and roots (especially roots) is able to reduce the growth of weeds, barnyardgrass. Acid residues of plant toxicity are attributed to Cyclic Hydroxamic. In addition Rye as a cover crop to increase genus comprises weed grass as barnyardgrass, *Ammania coccinea*, *Heteranthera limosa* and Cypress grass and in some cases has reduced pesticide.

Wheat growth of weed species in agronomic minimum inhibitory for later. Moreover, the ease of chemical control of this species, it is a good plant cover crops or mulch is named. Legumes, including species that are appropriate to deal with weeds. Most of these plants grow and the dense canopy, have a high capacity to compete with weeds. Legume species should be used as a living mulch. In one study it was found, when the subterranean clover (*Trifolium subtranium*) is used as a living mulch, plant *Ipomoea hederacea* and *Panicum dichotomiflorum* is able to prevent the growth of weeds and debris when cover crops of barley, rye, triticale, wheat and hairy vetch on seed germination and seedling emergence in the field are playing like *Amaranthus* genus comprises weed grass decreases. The remains of several species of clover (*Trifolium spp.*) also have a high potential for weed management in sorghum residue to prevent weeds from growing gardens and nursery for many applications. Report on allelopathic effect of water washing, steam and debris hemp (*Cannabis sativa*) on sorghum, mung beans, fenugreek Castor and observed.

The allelopathic effects of plant rue (*Ruta graveolens*) on seed germination of weed, chicken, Euphorbiaceae and Cypress grass has been reported. Saturated solution of coumarin in roots and lily bulbs in the study of about 2 to 3 hours to prevent mitotic division and its primary effect is similar to the procedure Colchicine the cell to the first mitosis of the coumarin was prevented. Rye residues in soils that are free of chemicals have accumulated in the soil and prevent weeds will grow Germination. This material stems from leakage of Rye identification have been removed. This material was dissolved in water and the leaching field crop residues are the roots of some crops and weeds are prevented. Allelopathic effects on plants, clover and vetch flower cluster crop plants and weeds, clover and vetch showed that increasing the concentration of the

aqueous extract of the flower cluster, growing seedlings (seedling) and germination of corn, cotton, mustard and wild morning glories reduced. Concentrated extracts of these two legumes, germination and growth of wild mustard and rye were wide open. The research Canola cultivation and weed control in field potatoes Sudan Grass indicated below the soil in spring rape, weed density by 85 and 73 percent, respectively, over the past two years to reduce. The weed biomass 95 and 50%, respectively, in the two years was reduced in the first year of the potato in the second year of fallow.

3.4 LIMITATION OF USING ALLELOPATHIC EFFECT

There are many limitations in using allelopathic potentiality as a weed management tool. The limitations are both because of plant itself, producing allelochemicals and the environmental condition. Many abiotic and biotic soil factors have influences on phytotoxic levels of allelochemicals. Various abiotic and biotic factors, such as plant age, temperature, light and soil conditions, microflora, nutritional status, and herbicide treatments influence the production and release of allelochemicals, although allelopathy is considered as a genetically influenced factor. While moving in the soil allelochemicals may undergo transformation as various factors regarding soil environment like physical, chemical, biological and physicochemical properties of soil may influence the activity of allelochemicals. So to study the allelopathic potentiality of a plant the role of soil should not be ignored. According to Inderjit and Dakshini (1995) many studies on allelopathy, however, do not involve soil rather involve an artificial soil substrate. After entry into soil allelochemicals may be toxified or detoxified by microbes. Inderjit and Dakshini (1994) found that the amounts of water-soluble phenolics in *P. lanceolata* leaf leachate amended soil varied depending on the soil textural classes (clay, sandy-loam, sand, and silty-loam). Clay mineralogy also plays important role in activity of allelochemicals. The cation exchange capacity, moisture holding capacity, concentration of inorganic ion etc. are dependable on the type of clay minerals. Oxidative polymerization of organic compounds is influenced by the clay-size layer silicates as mentioned by Huang et al. (1999).

Many allelochemicals are very much expensive to synthesize inspite of having excellent herbicidal properties as for example, tentoxin. Some allelochemicals are toxic to human beings and are carcinogenic, e. g. AAL-toxin and fumonisin are toxic to mammalian cells.

Sorgoleone, for example, is reported to cause dermatitis. The meals remaining after oil extraction is fed to livestock, but in limited amounts for glucosinolates are degraded by an endogenous enzyme, myrosinase (E.C. 3.2.3.1) to form in particular, isothiocyanates and thiocyanate ion, nitriles and oxazolidinethiones and these species have been found to be harmful when consumed by humans and animals and can, for example, cause thyroid, liver and kidney diseases in monogastric animals. Some allelopathic agents are active only under hot and dry climate as they work in vapor phase such as monoterpenes because the high vapour density of the essential oils may penetrate into soil, affecting adversely the undergrowing.

The amount of nutrient available to the plant and the efficiency of the plant to utilize the nutrient strongly influences the allelopathic potentiality of rice plant. Sometimes the deficiency of nutrients favors the production of secondary metabolites as mentioned by Hoagland and Williams (1985). As for example in aerobic P-deficient soil rice roots excrete organic anions particularly citrate to solubilize and enhance phosphorus uptake. The concentration of some inorganic ions affect the activity of allelochemicals. According to Cheng (1989) only the extent of Mn^{2+} and Fe^{2+} ions exposed to organic chemicals influence the oxidation of organic chemicals but the content of these ions do not play any direct role. Mn, Fe, Al, and Si oxides cause polymerization of phenolic compounds into humic acids; however, Mn oxide is the most powerful catalyst. Some allelochemicals affect the growth of the plant itself i. e., autotoxic effect which is another problem in the mechanism of allelopathy. As for example Yu and Matsui (1994) identified autotoxins, including some derivatives of benzoic and cinnamic acids from the root exudates of cucumber. Quan Yu (2003) showed the inhibitory effect of root exudates and aqueous root extracts of cucumber (*Cucumis sativus*) and allelochemicals on root antioxidant enzymes and leaf photosynthesis, transpiration and stomatal conductance in cucumber. Therefore while studying the role of allelopathy in controlling weeds the autotoxicity of plants should not be ignored. There must be some strong interaction among autotoxic chemicals and soil environment. In some areas of the world the phytotoxic effect of decomposing rice residues in the soil caused problem on next years crop.

3.5 FACTORS TO BE CONSIDERED IN USE OF ALLELOPATHY.

Before using allelopathy in weed management programmes there are a number of other factors that might be important in any given situation

- **Varieties**

There can be a great deal of difference in the strength of allelopathic effects between different crop varieties

- **Specificity**

There is a significant degree of specificity in allelopathic effects. Thus, a crop which is strongly allelopathic against one weed may show little or no effect against another

- **Autotoxicity**

Allelopathic chemicals may not only suppress the growth of other plant species, they can also suppress the germination or growth of seeds and plants of the same species. Lucerne is particularly well known for this and has been well researched. The toxic effect of wheat straw on following wheat crops is also well known

- **Crop on crop effects**

Residues from allelopathic crops can hinder germination and growth of following crops as well as weeds. A sufficient gap must be left before the following crop is sown. Larger seeded crops are effected less and transplants are not affected

- **Environmental factors**

Several factors impact on the strength of the allelopathic effect. These include pests and disease and especially soil fertility. Low fertility increases the production of allelochemicals. After incorporation the allelopathic effect declines fastest in warm wet conditions and slowest in cold wet conditions

- **Allelopathic weeds?**

Several weed species have been reported to show allelopathic properties. They include couch grass, creeping thistle and chickweed. Where they occur together they may have a synergistic negative effect on crops.

CHAPTER FOUR

DISCUSSION

Despite herbicidal activity of allelopathic plants, to attain significant weed reduction under field conditions a large quantity of plant materials or pellets is required. This needs heavy field work. Therefore, the possibility of its periodical application for greater weed control should be further examined. The various combinations of allelopathic plants and herbicides to reduce dependence on synthetic herbicides should be tested. In addition, a combination of different allelopathic plant species with strong weed-suppressing ability, may be capable of controlling more weed species than a single allelopathic plant species. Another alternative to reduce field work is to select allelochemicals from various sources, such as plants or microorganisms, and use them as herbicides in place of synthetic chemicals. This procedure can have desirable results, because most natural products are broken down rather rapidly by common microorganisms and thus are not persistent pollutants in the environment, as are many of the synthetic herbicides. Among the plant products as herbicides, juglone, isolated from walnut tree has been found effective against redroot pigweed, velvetleaf and barnyard grass. Caffeine derived from coffee showed considerable selectivity in inhibiting germination of *Amaranthus spinosus* L. at a concentration that has no effect on blackgram. Strigol, a sesquiterpenoid derivative from cotton roots is a potent germination stimulant of witchweed (*Striga asiatica* L. Kuntz), an obligate parasite of maize, sorghum and *Orobanche minor*. Dhurrin (sorghum); gallic acid (spurge); Phlorizin (apple root); trimethylxanthene (coffee) and cinch (eucalyptus) are some other important plant products having promising herbicidal activity. In this regard continuous study on isolation and identification of allelopathic compounds in plants and rhizosphere should be conducted. Although many biologically active compounds have been found, we still need to explore new compounds from plants and microorganisms.

CHAPTER FIVE

CONCLUSION

Increasing attention has been given to the role and potential of solarization and allelopathy as a management strategy for crop protection against weeds and other pests. Incorporating allelopathy into natural and agricultural management systems may reduce the use of herbicides, insecticides, and other pesticides, reducing environment/soil pollution. With respect to allelopathy, there is a great demand for compounds with selective toxicity that can be readily degraded by either the plant or by the soil microorganisms. In addition, plant, microorganisms, other soil organisms and insects can produce allelochemicals which provide new strategies for maintaining and increasing agricultural production in the future.

In spite of that some points we have to consider before implication of allelochemicals as natural herbicide:

(i) Firstly, along with laboratory experiments field experiments are exclusively needed to study its interaction with various physical, chemical, biological and physicochemical properties of soil.

(ii) Secondly the movement of allelochemicals, mode of action, selectivity etc should be broadly studied and

(iii) Finally the impact of use of allelochemicals from agronomic and environmental point of view needs special attention. Before use of any chemicals the security from environment point of view is to be taken into consideration. The dose, frequency and method of application determine the extent of toxicity of a chemical. The acceptance of allelochemicals is much depended on this context.

However , the use of crop allelopathic properties and soil solarization are both environmentally very good.

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